

Telecommunications and Innovation: A Global Study of Broadband, Telephone, and Mobile Cellular Access

Yagha R Joshi ¹ and Alison Watts ²

¹Email: yagha.joshi@siu.edu, Southern Illinois University
Carbondale, Carbondale, IL 62901, USA

²Email: wattsa@siu.edu, Southern Illinois University
Carbondale, Carbondale, IL 62901, USA

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Abstract: This study investigates the relationship between access to broadband, telephone, and mobile cellular services and innovation in 190 countries from 2000 to 2018, using data from the World Bank. The analysis employs both Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and fixed effect regression methods and examines the influence of a country's income level on the observed correlation. The findings of this research reveal a positive and robust association between communication infrastructure and innovation. Two potential explanations are explored: (i) increasing marginal benefits of broadband deployment and (ii) the creation of positive externalities that indirectly boost innovation. Notably, these positive effects are consistent across countries with varying income levels.

Keywords: Broadband, Innovation, Patent, Trademark, Fixed-Effect
JEL Classification Code: O31, O33, O34, O36

1 Introduction

Broadband has changed the way people work. An efficient and reliable IT infrastructure produces the finest conditions for business, innovation, and eServices, both public and private. IT enables people to access the services they require, no matter where they are. Economists and policymakers are interested in quantifying the effect of information technology and communication in innovation. The investment in broadband infrastructure is on the rise throughout the world, but there is little scientific evidence to substantiate this hypothesis.

The intellectual property (IP) serves as the foundation of innovation in the economy. IP rights work as an incentive for discovery and creativity and provide inventors with an opportunity to profit from the value of their innovative work. Protection of IP reduces the transaction costs between inventors and industry by providing information about the quality of the invention without jeopardizing the ownership of the idea. The trademarks may not directly stimulate innovation, yet innovating and non-innovating firms extensively use trademarks. The trademarks can differentiate the products or services, work as a signal of quality (goodwill), reduce consumer search costs, and signal other firms to be innovative (Davis 2006). Davis (2006) further suggests that trademarks can positively affect a firm's incentives to innovate by providing direct incentives to engage in incremental innovation, particularly product differentiation.

Mobile phones have developed into one of the principal communication devices in all countries, and they have been progressively applied to access the Internet. In low and middle-income countries, where adequate telecommunications infrastructure often remains to lag that of richer economies, the growing affordability and significant penetration rates of mobiles of handsets are helping millions of new users approach the Internet. The mobile phone is supposed to become the dominant tool for accessing the World Wide Web and many new Internet-based applications. Mobile cellular and the mobile Internet together already constitute the greatest information and distribution

network in the world (Tim Kelly 2010). This linkage is of the usefulness of the mobile devices can extend Internet connection, and with it, the know-how, services, and business capabilities to millions of users in developing markets, notably in rural sections. Due to low costs of infrastructure roll-out, ease of use, the availability of inexpensive phones, and flexible subscription plans, the mobile cellular subscription is supposed to skyrocket in the countries characterized by comparatively low levels of income. A collection of investigations documents a high interrelationship between a country's income level and connectivity. In low-income countries, the manufacture, processing, and transfer of knowledge/information are comparatively more costly because of weak telecommunications infrastructure (Donner and Escobari, 2010).

In this article, we examine how broadband internet affects innovation. Our context is the adoption of broadband internet around the world over the period 2000-2018. Our analysis employs data available at the development indicator of the world bank for 190 countries. This gives us information over time and across countries' number of patents and trademarks.

Because of limited funding, broadband access was progressively rolled out across the countries around the globe, so the infrastructure was established in different countries at different times. Conditional on year and country fixed effects; we argue that the spatial and temporal variation in the availability of broadband across the countries is plausibly exogenous.

We exploited the classification made by the World Bank (WB) for the countries based on GNI per capita. UN classifies countries into four income levels: low, lower-middle, upper-middle, and high-income countries. We combine lower middle-and upper-middle-income countries to make middle-income countries. We begin by estimating the effect of broadband on innovation across the countries by OLS. We find that broadband has a higher impact on innovation in high-income countries, while telephone has a higher effect on middle and low-income countries.

After performing fixed effect estimation, we explore our results are consistent with the results got from OLS. As we controlled for a country, and year fixed effects, the broadband coefficients are smaller in the fixed-effect model.

We find significant effects of broadband, fixed telephone, and mobile cellular subscription on patents and trademarks using a country and time fixed effects model: moving from no broadband subscription to full availability increases the percentage of patents' application filed by 1.49 percentage points. If we observe the result on the impact of broadband on trademarks, we can see that every 100-percentage rise in broadband is associated with a 1.08 percent increase in the number of trademarks. Similarly, having fixed telephone increases patents by 5.67 percentage points, and moving from no mobile cellular to full availability increases the number of patents filed by 1.70 percentage points. As stated in the literature, we can see the effect of broadband in innovation is higher in high-income countries as high-income countries have higher purchasing capacity, better communication infrastructure, this enables them to reduce the information cost (Xu, Watts and Reed 2019) and hence higher innovation.

We have built on previous research in three ways. First, we have information on countries based on the income level. This distinction allows us to see the pattern of broadband and phone subscription among the countries. The results show that high-income countries employ broadband more intensively, while low and middle-income countries use telephone and mobile services more extensively because of less cost. Second, we employed a GMM estimator to see whether the number of patents last year affects the patent this year and found that patents last year created a positive externality and induces high patents this year. Third, we employ non-linear specifications to see whether there is an increasing or decreasing marginal benefit of employing these services. We found evidence that there is an increasing marginal benefit of broadband deployment. The marginal benefit is bigger in high-income countries be due to better infrastructure, bigger investment, the higher purchasing power of households in high-income countries.

This study has potential limitations. We employed our dependent variable and all other variables as per hundred. The dependent variable is patent per 100 people. Because of the unavailability of the data, we are uncertain to separate the patents filed through institutions and individuals. It might

be possible sometimes that those who have a broadband connection at home might not be using it for the research activity, and it might bias, hence the result obtained from the data and there is a possibility of selection bias. In the same way, those applying for a patent through an institution might have worked at home by using the broadband connection at home.

The paper proceeds as follows: The next section briefly reviews the related literature. In Section 2.3, we discuss the data and descriptive statistics. Section 2.4 presents the econometric model and results. Section 2.5 concludes.

2 Literature Review

There is a comprehensive research on the effect of innovation in economic growth (Nelson & Winter, 1982; Bessant, 1991; Nonaka, 1991; Greenhalgh and Rogers, 2010; Naomi, 2012; Gordon, 2012; Petrariu et al., 2013; Capello et al., 2013; Pece et al., 2015; Adak, 2015; Fan et al., 2017; Pianta, 2017; Korableva et al., 2018; Thompson, 2018; Shachmurove, 2018; Bernier and Plouffe, 2019; Broughel et al., 2019; Roberts et al., 2019) but insufficient consideration has been given to the effects of the Internet on innovation. Various authors employ patents (Igami & Subrahmanyam 2019; Daly et al. 2019; Dang et al. 2015; German-Soto et al. 2013; Bode 2004; Acs et al. 2002; Baptista and Swann 1998; Anselin, Varga, and Acs 1997; Acs, Archibugi 1992; Acs & Audretsch 1989) and trademark (Castaldi 2019; Morales et al. 2018; De Vries et al. 2017; Gotsch, Matthias, and Christiane Hipp 2012; Millot 2009; Malmberg 2005) as the indicators of innovation. Different aspects of broadband Internet technology have been studied previously. Akerman et al. (2015) examined access to broadband Internet worsens the productivity of unskilled workers. Atasoy (2013) investigates the effects of the expansion of broadband Internet connection from 1999 to 2007 on labor market results throughout the United States and established that obtaining a connection to broadband services in a county is associated with approximately a 1.8 percentage point rise in the employment rate, with greater effects in rural and isolated areas. Gruber (2001) analyzes the determinants of the dispersion of mobile telecommunications in Central

and Eastern Europe and found that the diffusion speed is quicker in countries that have adopted mobile telecommunications recently. He further suggested that the pace of diffusion increases in the size of the fixed telecommunications network. Sung and Lee (2002), with Korean provincial panel data for the period 1991–1998, study the impact of the speedy increase in mobile telephones on the access demand for conventional fixed telephones. Their research shows that a 1% increase in the number of mobile telephones results in a reduction of 0.10–0.18% in new fixed telephone connections and a 0.14–0.22% rise in fixed disconnections. Christine (2009), in a study-related of 120 countries, concludes that every 10-percentage point increase in the penetration of mobile phones is associated with an increase in the economic growth of 0.81 percentage points in developing countries and 0.60 percentage points in developed countries.

The literature on the association between innovation and the broadband Internet, fixed telephone, and mobile cellular is much smaller. Sawhney et al. (2005) studied how broadband affects the process of collaborative innovation and discovered that the distinctive capacities of the Internet as a platform for consumer engagement, including interactivity, increased reach, persistence, speed, and flexibility, and recommend that organizations can employ these capabilities to involve customers in collaborative product innovation through a variety of Internet-based mechanisms. Yoo et al. (2005) analyze the expansion of the mobile infrastructure in South Korea. Their research shows that successful innovation and diffusion of broadband mobile services are positively correlated. Muchiri and Karume (2016) established that there are positive roles broadband plays in spurring innovations in Kenya.

The paper closely related to ours is Xu, Watts, and Reed (2019), who examined how internet accessibility lowers information costs and boosts regional innovation activity by taking county-level datasets in the US. They found a positive relationship between the access to the Internet (with a speed of 10 Mbps) and the number of patents filed in that specific county.

3 Data and Descriptive Statistics

To quantify the effects of broadband deployment on innovation, we sourced data on the number of patent and trademark applications filed by residents from the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). The number of patents and trademarks is then converted into per 100.

The data on our independent variables: broadband access, telephone, and cellular mobile, is taken from the development indicators of the World Bank. All of our independent variables are taken per hundreds of the total population of the country. It is supposed that innovation activity is positively correlated with the expenditure on research and development. R & D expenditure as a percentage of GDP is one of our control variables. People between the ages of 15 to 64 are supposed more active physically and mentally, so we control for the mentioned age group. Education level is another variable that is assumed to be influential for innovation. It is clear in the records that the number of patents is significantly higher for people with higher education. Most of our socioeconomic data appear from organizational records maintained by the World Bank. Specifically, we employ a longitudinal database that encloses each country from 2000 to 2018. It comprises individual demographic information of the countries regarding age, socioeconomic data (educational attainment, income, employment status).

To instigate how the relationship between broadband and innovation varies in various income level countries around the globe, we employ the classification made by World Bank. As of 1 July 2019, the World Bank classified low-income economies are those with a GNI per capita, of \$1,025 or less in 2018; lower-middle-income economies are those with a GNI per capita between \$1,026 and \$3, 995; upper-middle-income economies are those between \$3,996 and \$12, 375; high-income economies are those with a GNI per capita of \$12,376 or more. This classification of countries based on income level allows us to control for the effect of income on innovation, as people are supposed to be more innovative with higher income.

There is a variation among countries at the starting time, speed of broad-

band and telephone services. As discussed by Nina et al. (2011), the broadband penetration appeared most countries in years 1999, Canada (1997), the United States (1998), Hungary (2001) and Ireland (2002).

Table 1: Summary statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max
Patent app(res.)	2351	77387.11	237310.9	1	2161610
Trademark app(res.)	2597	144340.1	401711.1	1	3957315
Broadband per 100	3692	8.683	11.376	0	45.42
Fixed Telephone per 100	4553	19.815	19.639	0.0004	135.6037
Mobile cellular per 100	4508	68.722	48.804	0.0181	328.7904
R & D Exp.(% of GDP)	1605	.934	.953	.00544	4.57606
Primary school enrollment	3023	88.735	11.724	26.82781	99.95587
Secondary school enrollment	2633	67.934	23.712	3.27968	99.91164
Pop. with BS degree(% of total)	355	16.722	8.99	0.8055	46.56201
Pop. with MS degree(% of total)	277	6.042	5.929	0.125	28.15081
Pop. with PhD degree(% of total)	236	.55	.541	0.011	2.97441
Pop. age 0-14(% of total pop)	4314	29.712	10.477	11.0484	50.26395
Pop. age 15-64(% of total pop)	4314	62.722	6.771	47.18344	86.39825
Pop age 65 and more(% of total pop)	4314	7.566	5.127	.6855916	27.10948
GNI per capita(2010 USD)	4752	9239.856	15955.49	110	119073.6
GDP per capita(2010 USD)	4409	13642.23	20483.22	194.8731	193745.6
ICT import(% of goods import)	3558	7.578	6.14	.0033181	51.85921

Table 1 displays summary statistics for the data we employed. We present the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviations of all the variables we employed in our study. As we can see from table, there is tremendous variation in the number of patent and trademark application by residents across the countries. The average number of Patent and trademark are 77387 and 144344, respectively. Out of 100 people living in a country, only eight people have broadband access. The minimum value of broadband per 100 is 0 in Haiti and Congo, and maximum is 45.42 in Switzerland, which clearly shows there is a variation in broadband subscribers across the countries.

We present the graphs for selected countries where we plot number of trademark and patent application by residents. Since broadband is started in the world from the early 2000 in most of the countries, we can clearly see a rapid increase in the number of patent and trademark applications in all countries we have selected. We can see, in the figures, that there is increasing

Figure 1: India

Figure 2: China

Figure 3: USA

Figure 4: South Korea

Figure 5: Nepal

Figure 6: Bangladesh

trend of patent and trademark applications over the time.

4 Econometric Model and Results

We estimate in impact of broadband, fixed telephone and mobile cellular in the number of patents and trademarks filed by residents by two methods: OLS and country fixed effects.

4.1 Ordinary Least Square

To estimate the effect of broadband on the number of patent and trademark applications across the countries, we employ the population regression method known as ordinary least squares. To estimate the relationship by OLS first, we calculate the average of all the variables in the model. We specify the model as follows:

$$y_i = \alpha + \beta x_i + \gamma M_i + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where y_i has two possibilities: number of Patents and Trademarks filed by residents per hundred, x_i may take three values: broadband subscription per 100, fixed telephone per hundred and mobile cellular per 100 and M is set of control variables like population of age between 15 to 64, level of education and investment in research and development as a percentage of GDP.

4.1.1 Patents:

In this section, we present the results obtained from OLS taking patent per 100 as the dependent variable. The independent variables are broadband per 100, fixed telephone per 100, and mobile cellular per 100.

In table 2, we present the results obtained by including all independent variables and adding ICT import as a control variable. The coefficients of telephone and mobile cellular are higher in low and middle-income countries compared to high-income countries.

As telephone and mobile cellular subscriptions are cheaper than broadband, which enables low-income countries to use a high number of telephones than broadband but higher-income countries can afford broadband and may replace traditional telephones by it. The results indicate that there is posi-

Table 2: Impact of broadband on patents filed by residents

VARIABLES	All	Low	Middle	High
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0676 (0.0472)	0.0606*** (0.0605)	0.0262*** (0.0632)	0.0706*** (0.0926)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.248*** (0.0677)	0.505*** (0.0959)	0.994*** (0.0876)	0.468*** (0.119)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	0.700*** (0.0924)	0.781*** (0.0802)	0.657*** (0.134)	.476*** (0.179)
ln(secondary)	0.831*** (0.0997)	0.977*** (0.164)	0.581*** (0.154)	1.258*** (0.148)
ln(population age 15-64)	1.138*** (0.0133)	1.455*** (0.0235)	1.136*** (0.0184)	1.046*** (0.0212)
ln(ICT import)	-0.162*** (0.0414)	0.452*** (0.0516)	-0.232*** (0.0532)	0.0613 (0.0655)
ln(R & D)	0.526*** (0.0256)	0.576*** (0.0230)	0.467*** (0.0412)	0.637*** (0.0412)
Constant	-15.65*** (0.539)	-32.42*** (0.893)	-14.53*** (1.038)	-13.04*** (0.750)
Observations	1,785	169	960	656
R-squared	0.913	0.994	0.920	0.916

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

tive and significant relation between broadband access and number of patents' applications. Every 1 percentage increase in broadband access is associated with 0.06 percentage points increase in the number of patent application in low-income countries as compared to 0.7 percentage points in high-income countries.

4.1.2 Trademarks:

In this section we present the results obtained from OLS regression by taking trademarks per 100 as dependent variable. The independent variables we take are broadband per 100, fixed telephone per 100, and mobile cellular per 100.

Results in table 3 indicate that every 1 percent increase in broadband

Table 3: Impact of broadband on trademarks application

VARIABLES	All	Low	Middle	High
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0683 (0.0422)	0.0224*** (0.0527)	0.0241*** (0.0603)	0.0382** (0.0889)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.651*** (0.0626)	0.642*** (0.0804)	1.258*** (0.0841)	0.495*** (0.114)
ln(mobile cellular per 100)	0.317*** (0.0868)	0.521*** (0.0856)	0.986*** (0.125)	0.292* (0.166)
ln(secondary)	0.543*** (0.0960)	1.820*** (0.183)	0.340** (0.152)	1.208*** (0.141)
ln(population age 15-64)	1.086*** (0.0125)	1.038*** (0.0267)	1.225*** (0.0173)	0.921*** (0.0193)
ln(ictimport)	0.262*** (0.0405)	0.241*** (0.0548)	0.374*** (0.0517)	0.308*** (0.0610)
ln(R & D)	-0.0260 (0.0250)	0.192*** (0.0259)	-0.415*** (0.0404)	0.163*** (0.0392)
Constant	-15.60*** (0.525)	-20.35*** (1.004)	-21.59*** (0.988)	-12.15*** (0.716)
Observations	1,835	185	968	682
R-squared	0.888	0.987	0.914	0.872

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

access is associated with 0.022 percentage points increase in the number of trademark applications in low-income countries while it is 0.038 percentage in case of high-income countries justifying that high-income countries are intensively employing broadband than low and middle-income countries. If we observe the coefficient of telephone per 100 and mobile cellular per 100, we can see coefficients are bigger in low and middle-income countries than high-income countries. As broadband is more expensive than telephone and mobile cellular, the results are consistent with the notion of purchasing capacity determines what to buy.

4.2 Fixed Effects Estimator

Our empirical specification exploits the panel structure of the data: country fixed effects absorb any permanent heterogeneity at the country level. As we see in the summary statistics, there is a variation among the countries in the timing of broadband deployment. This model help control for omitted variable bias because of unobserved heterogeneity when this heterogeneity is constant over time.

Hsiao (2007) mentioned that dealing with the impact of omitted variables is much easier in the panel data because panel data comprise information on both the inter-temporal dynamics and the identity of individuals. Our specification for fixed effect regression is as given below.

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta X_{it} + \gamma C_{it} + \delta_i + \lambda_t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Here, the dependent variable Y_{it} has two possibilities: (i) number of patents filed by per 100 residents, and (ii) number trademarks filed by 100 residents. Right-hand side variables are same as OLS specification. δ_c is the country fixed effect and λ_t is year fixed effect. C_{it} is the set of controls used in our study.

4.2.1 Patents

Table 4 present the results obtained by including all independent variables. As we can see, as a high-income country moves from no broadband availability to full access, filing of patents increase by 3.28% points in an average, which is significantly higher than low (0.0181) and middle (0.0161) income countries. The coefficients of telephone and mobile cellular are higher in low (1.01) and middle-income countries (0.403) than high-income countries (0.327) supporting the conclusion we get from OLS. Since the unobserved heterogeneity due to omitted variable bias is taken care by fixed effects model, the coefficients for all independent variables are smaller than in OLS. (1) of the table 4, as usual, represents how patent application by residents is affected by broadband for low-income countries. The result is consistent with previous ones. Again,

Table 4: Impact of broadband on patents filed by residents: Fixed effects

VARIABLES	All	Low	Middle	High
ln(Broadband per 100)	0.0149* (0.0118)	0.0181** (0.0937)	0.0161** (0.0164)	0.0328*** (0.0179)
ln(Telephone per 100)	0.0567 (0.0837)	1.011* (0.521)	0.403** (0.145)	0.327*** (0.0979)
ln(Mobile cellular per 100)	0.0170 (0.0275)	0.275 (0.433)	0.0339 (0.0397)	0.0336 (0.0349)
ln(secondary)	1.277*** (0.208)	6.201*** (1.974)	0.995*** (0.284)	1.474*** (0.320)
ln(R & D Exp.)	0.326*** (0.0567)	-0.0305 (0.327)	0.421*** (0.0956)	0.260*** (0.0694)
ln(ICT import)	0.0842* (0.0488)	0.784* (0.391)	0.0116 (0.0611)	0.324*** (0.0866)
ln(pop15-64)	2.320*** (0.325)	3.100 (2.260)	2.271*** (0.448)	1.970*** (0.487)
Constant	-34.08*** (5.053)	-9.305 (30.53)	-34.76*** (6.930)	-28.05*** (7.735)
Observations	930	47	514	369
R-squared	0.200	0.504	0.235	0.232
Number of countries	88	8	46	34
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

the coefficient of broadband is statistically significant and has a high magnitude than that in low and middle-income countries. Similarly, as expected, coefficient of telephone is still bigger than high-income countries.

Extra control variables like ICT imports expressed in terms of percent of total goods import, we add log of the number of researchers per 100 people and population density with the newly constructed data set for 10 the high-income countries. The data covers from 2000 to 2017.

In table 5, we wanted to see how the dependent and independent variables are correlated after adding more control variables. The dependent variable in each column of table 14 is the log (patent per 100). In column (1) the variable

Table 5: Impact of broadband, telephone and mobile cellular on patents

	(1)	(2)	(3)
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0572*** (2.88)		
ln(R & D)	0.751*** (5.20)	0.659*** (4.40)	0.841*** (6.31)
ln(secondary)_100	2.611*** (8.87)	2.477*** (7.57)	2.236*** (8.10)
ln(researcher per 100)	0.530** (3.07)	0.738*** (4.07)	0.302 (1.82)
ict import(% of imports)	0.0591*** (7.80)	0.0561*** (7.16)	0.0566*** (8.24)
ln(pop15-64)	15.04*** (9.52)	16.02*** (7.20)	13.03*** (8.84)
ln(population density)	-11.95*** (-5.92)	-13.04*** (-4.84)	-10.94*** (-5.93)
ln(telephone per)100		0.107 (0.86)	
ln(mobile per 100)			0.497*** (5.36)
constant	-179.0*** (-10.22)	-192.0*** (-7.60)	-154.1*** (-9.32)
Country FE	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES
Observations	111	111	111
R-squared	0.829	0.766	0.892
Number of countries	10	10	10

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

of interest is broadband subscription per 100 people. Even after including more control variables in the baseline fixed effects model, the coefficient of broadband per 100 is positively associated with the number of patents application by 100 residents and is statistically significant. For every 10 percent increase in the broadband subscription in the selected high-income countries, there is about a 0.6 percent increase in the number of patents application filed by residents. The variable of interest in column (2) of table 2.5 is log of fixed telephone per 100. There is a positive correlation between the number of patent applications and the number of fixed telephone subscriptions. The result is consistent with that we get in table 4. Finally, column (3) of the table 5 shows that there is statistically significant positive association between the number of patent applications and subscription of mobile cellular.

4.2.2 Trademarks

This subsection presents the results of how trademarks are correlated with broadband per hundred, fixed telephone per 100, and mobile cellular per hundred.

Table 6 presents the effect of broadband in the number of trademark application by residents. When we include all independent variables in our model, we get a positive and significant effect. Column (1) of table 6 states that for everyone, percentage increases in the number of broadband access, there is 0.01 percentage rise in the number of trademark application by residents in an average. In high-income countries, for one percentage increase in broadband access is associated with a 0.78 percentage increase in the number of trademarks. When we see that effect for low and middle-income countries, each one percentage rise in broadband access is accompanied by 0.6 percentage and 0.5 percentage increase in the number of trademark application by, respectively.

4.3 Generalized Method of Moments

We want to see whether the patents last year affect the patents this year. Number of patents is the sign of active research people are doing, which is

supposed to be induced by higher investment and broadband availability. If there is an economic slowdown, the patent applications are most likely to decrease. Is there any positive externality created by the patents last year? To answer this question also we want to use system GMM.

Unlike static panel data models, dynamic panel data models include lagged levels of the dependent variable as regressors. The Arellano–Bond estimator uses generalized method of moments estimation rather than instrumental variables estimation. In the Arellano–Bond method, first differences of the regression equation are taken to eliminate the fixed effects. Then, deeper lags of the dependent variable instruments for differenced lags of the dependent variable (which are endogenous). The GMM estimators are consistent, asymptotically normal, and efficient in the class of all estimators that do not use any extra information aside from that contained in the moment conditions.

4.3.1 Model Specification

In this section, We specified the model as given below.

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \phi Y_{i(t-1)} + \beta X_{it} + \gamma M_{it} + \delta_i + \lambda_t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

As in the fixed effects model, the dependent variable Y_{it} has two possibilities: (i) number of patents filed by residents, and (ii) number trademarks filled by residents. $Y_{i(t-1)}$ is the value of dependent variable at year $t - 1$. On the right-hand side, the variables of the interest X_{it} represent broadband subscription per 100, fixed telephone subscription per 100, and mobile cellular subscription per 100. The set of control variables are enrollment rate at secondary level education, percentage of population between the age of 15 to 64, and investment in research and development as a percentage of GDP. δ_i is the country fixed effects. λ_t is year fixed effects.

Order	z	$prob. > z$
1	-2.274	0.0230
2	-.93649	0.3490

Arellano-Bond test for zero auto-correlation in first-differenced errors is presented here: the null hypothesis is: no auto-correlation. We reject no auto-correlation of order 1 and cannot reject no auto-correlation of order 2. There is evidence that the Arellano-Bond model assumptions are satisfied.

4.3.2 Results

Table 7 presents the results got from Arellano- Bond estimator. As we can see from the table 7, coefficient of patents, last year is positive and significant except for low-income countries, which showed that patent last year has positive externalities. In other words, we can say, the country that filed high applications last year more likely to apply for higher number patents this year too. Broadband coefficient remains statistically significant and positive for all countries. Magnitude of the broadband coefficient remains bigger for high-income countries (.022) compared to low (0.0187) and middle (0.0206) income countries.

The table 8 presents the results of the system GMM taking trademark per 100 as the dependent variable. Here, we want to see how last year's trademark applications affect the number of trademarks this year.

The coefficients of trademarks last year are statistically significant and positive, showing that there is positive externality created by last year's trademarks to this year. Broadband coefficient is positive and significant with higher magnitude for high-income countries, while the coefficient of telephone is higher in low and middle-income countries as expected.

4.4 Non-Linear Specification

The construction of a non-linear model is key and appropriate time of differentiation with suggested designs. The infer for this choice is that the relationship between the explanatory variables, and the dependent variable may be non-linear. We demonstrated this by working out a linear model for broadband per 100 whose explanatory power and coefficient of variation were substantially higher restricted than those of its corresponding non-linear

model, and second, by demonstrating that scatter plots of residuals versus some of the independent variables displayed a quadratic pattern.

Our key intention in this study to use a non-linear model is to know whether there are increasing (or decreasing) marginal benefits of broadband deployment.

We specify non-linear model as below:

$$Y_i = \alpha + \beta_1 X_i + \beta_2 X_i^2 + \gamma M_i + \epsilon_i \quad (4)$$

The set of control and independent variables remains same as in the base-line model. X_i^2 is the square of broadband, fixed telephone and mobile cellular.

4.4.1 Results

In this section, we present the results obtained from the non-linear specification. The coefficients of "*Broadband*²" is smaller than that of "Broadband" for all countries. For instance, a 10 percent increase in broadband access triggered an average increase of 8 percentage points in the number of patents filed by residents in high-income countries, and it is diminished and just increases by 0.63 percentage points when use non-linear form. The results are robust with middle and low-income countries, too. Similarly, the coefficients of "telephone" and "*telephone*²" are also diminishing. For all countries, irrespective of their income levels, the coefficients of squared terms are smaller than the non-squared terms of the same independent variables. These result supports our assumption that there is increasing marginal benefit of broadband deployment. Although the picture is not clear in case of telephone in low and middle-income countries, coefficients of mobile cellular clearly indicate that there is increasing marginal benefit if mobile cellular connection.

Table 9 present the results obtained from non-linear model where the dependent variable is the number of patents per 100. We can see the coefficients of *broadband* and *broadband*² are both positive, showing that there is increasing marginal benefit of broadband. The marginal benefit is increasing at an increasing rate and higher for high-income countries than in low- and middle-

income countries.

Table 10 presents the results from the non-linear model taking log of trademarks per 100 as a dependent variable. We can see, the coefficients of level and square term both are positive with broadband, showing that marginal benefits of employing broadband increases over time. The results for trademarks are not as clear as patents but still indicate that marginal benefits of broadband are higher in rich countries than in low and middle-income countries.

Table 6: Impact of broadband on trademarks filed by residents

VARIABLES	All	Low	Middle	High
lnbroadband_100	0.0108* (0.0653)	0.0507* (0.0285)	0.0624** (0.0815)	0.0785*** (0.0107)
lntelephone_100	0.354*** (0.0476)	0.0150 (0.234)	0.297*** (0.0731)	0.365*** (0.0603)
lncellular_100	0.0180 (0.0157)	0.127 (0.146)	-0.0102 (0.0202)	0.0882*** (0.0217)
lnsecondary	0.597*** (0.111)	-0.445 (0.859)	0.714*** (0.142)	0.292* (0.172)
lnrndexp	0.0878*** (0.326)	0.161 (0.117)	0.0548 (0.485)	0.335*** (0.483)
lnictimport	0.113*** (0.0271)	0.480*** (0.175)	0.0278 (0.0305)	0.248*** (0.0535)
lnpop1564	1.825*** (0.187)	2.371** (0.887)	1.877*** (0.248)	0.255 (0.321)
Constant	-29.07*** (2.913)	-42.00*** (10.15)	-29.38*** (3.898)	-6.142 (5.056)
Observations	947	54	510	383
R-squared	0.244	0.792	0.248	0.392
Number of countries	93	9	49	35
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 7: Impact of broadband on trademarks filed by residents

VARIABLES	All	Low	Middle	High
Lag of ln(patent per 100)	0.213*** (0.00258)	-0.281 (0.215)	0.591*** (0.0263)	0.227*** (0.0417)
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0143*** (0.00191)	0.0187 (0.159)	0.0206*** (0.00540)	0.0225*** (0.00417)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.179*** (0.0123)	0.844 (2.906)	0.427*** (0.0456)	0.0774 (0.112)
ln(cellular per 100)	0.0722*** (0.00666)	-0.410 (0.433)	0.0591*** (0.0186)	0.0144 (0.0349)
ln(secondary)	0.472*** (0.0228)	4.753 (3.906)	0.431*** (0.127)	0.649 (0.443)
ICT import	0.0309*** (0.000632)	0.165** (0.0825)	0.0277*** (0.00221)	0.0210*** (0.00221)
ln(R & D)	0.318*** (0.00457)	0.775 (0.532)	0.101*** (0.0227)	0.0147 (0.0540)
ln(population age 15-64)	0.829*** (0.0447)	8.675 (5.969)	-0.202 (0.218)	2.310** (1.050)
Constant	-21.59*** (0.798)	-106.2 (106.6)	-1.717 (3.477)	-46.69*** (14.83)
Observations	705	21	398	286
Number of id	68	4	38	26
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 8: Results of Arellano-Bond Estimator

VARIABLES	(1) All	(2) Low	(3) Middle	(4) High
Lag of ln(patent per 100)	0.503*** (0.00814)	0.441** (0.191)	0.613*** (0.0176)	0.466*** (0.0682)
ln(broadband per 100)	0.0150*** (0.00144)	0.113 (0.0965)	0.0161*** (0.00190)	0.0217*** (0.00711)
ln(telephone per 100)	0.0953*** (0.0150)	2.385** (1.170)	0.0547* (0.0301)	0.168*** (0.0274)
ln(cellular per 100)	0.0185*** (0.00580)	0.452* (0.272)	0.00762 (0.0124)	0.0754*** (0.0253)
ln(secondary)	0.0921*** (0.0276)	-1.113 (1.654)	0.0942 (0.158)	0.0572 (0.209)
ICT import	0.00994*** (0.00100)	0.146*** (0.0400)	0.00678*** (0.00155)	0.00301 (0.00397)
ln(R & D)	0.0275*** (0.00872)	0.402** (0.160)	0.0446** (0.0223)	0.396** (0.164)
ln(population 15-64)	0.518*** (0.155)	2.910 (1.790)	0.177 (0.214)	-0.195 (0.775)
Constant	-9.431*** (2.529)	-57.54** (25.43)	-3.189 (3.623)	1.273 (11.67)
Observations	721	27	392	302
Number of id	74	5	41	28
Country FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 9: Results of Non-Linear Specification I

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	All Countries	Low income	Middle income	High Income
(broadband per 100)	0.0796 (0.21)	0.321*** (21.19)	0.338*** (6.89)	0.488*** (4.94)
(broadband per 100) ²	0.0461*** (6.38)	0.0721 (1.31)	0.112*** (11.40)	0.0629* (2.11)
(telephone per 100)	1.055*** (19.10)	5.805*** (9.90)	0.668*** (6.26)	1.173*** (6.92)
(telephone per 100) ²	0.0333* (2.03)	-0.225 (-1.83)	-0.0294 (-1.12)	0.0545** (1.56)
(mobile cellular per 100)	5.673*** (12.73)	2.024* (2.20)	2.023** (2.89)	4.989** (3.05)
(mobile cellular per 100) ²	0.826*** (14.26)	0.276** (2.61)	0.344*** (3.73)	0.727*** (3.88)
(secondary)	0.974*** (11.60)	-0.840* (-2.33)	1.355*** (9.19)	1.311*** (6.65)
(population age 15-64)	1.112*** (86.44)	1.320*** (38.59)	1.135*** (59.03)	1.085*** (48.03)
(R and D)	0.428*** (16.11)	0.811*** (17.12)	0.316*** (6.39)	0.506*** (10.38)
constant	-28.26*** (-31.02)	-16.95*** (-5.93)	-23.12*** (-15.99)	-27.99*** (-8.30)
<i>N</i>	1980	216	1062	702

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 10: Results of Non-Linear Specification II

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	All Countries	Low income	Middle income	High Income
(broadband per 100)	0.290*** (7.53)	0.215* (2.42)	0.298 (0.06)	0.413*** (4.88)
(broadband per 100) ²	0.0128 (1.66)	0.0463 (1.82)	0.0639*** (6.52)	0.386*** (15.47)
(telephone per 100)	0.390*** (6.80)	1.129*** (6.94)	1.437*** (13.69)	1.621*** (11.26)
(telephone per 100) ²	-0.00574 (-0.33)	-0.123* (-2.41)	-0.0400 (-1.53)	-0.386*** (-12.84)
(mobile cellular per 100)	2.457*** (5.29)	1.792*** (4.02)	3.649*** (5.37)	8.257*** (6.22)
(mobile cellular per 100) ²	0.361*** (5.96)	0.281*** (4.61)	0.576*** (6.49)	0.881*** (5.78)
(secondary)	0.588*** (6.74)	1.599*** (11.48)	-0.461** (-3.12)	-0.197 (-1.23)
(population 15-64)	1.141*** (90.72)	1.062*** (39.40)	1.245*** (71.42)	1.050*** (60.95)
(R and D)	-0.0508 (-1.83)	0.298*** (13.37)	-0.300*** (-6.33)	0.128** (3.15)
constant	-10.79*** (-11.11)	-15.13*** (-14.38)	-8.760*** (-5.98)	-29.30*** (-10.65)
<i>N</i>	2052	234	1080	738

Standard errors in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

5 Conclusion

The effects of broadband, telephone and mobile cellular on innovation have become an important policy issue. We employ the World Bank data to analyze how access to broadband, telephone, and mobile cellular affects innovation. We exploit the panel structure of the data set to eliminate permanent heterogeneity at the country level. We find significant effects of broadband, fixed telephone and mobile cellular subscription on patents and trademarks using a country and time fixed effects model: moving from no broadband subscription to full availability increases the percentage of patents application filed by 1.49 percentage points. In case of trademarks, moving from no subscription of broadband, telephone and mobile cellular to full access to these facilities increases trademarks application by 1.08 percentage points. The effect broadband on the number of patents and trademarks is larger in high-income countries. We interpret this effect as the purchasing power of the citizens in the countries. As broadband is expensive compared to telephone and mobile cellular subscription, only few people in low-income countries can afford it. As expected, the effect of telephone on patents application is higher in low- and middle-income countries. Similarly, effects of mobile cellular on trademark application are bigger in developing nations.

We employed dynamic panel data model (System GMM) to see whether the patents this year are affected by the patents last year. The coefficient of lag of patent per 100 is statistically significant and positive, showing that patents this is is affected by the patents last year. We may interpret this effect as positive externality, which is indirect effect inducing the countries to file more patents and trademarks this year if it was that case last year.

Further, by observing the results obtained from non-linear specification, we can say that marginal benefit of having broadband is increasing at the increasing rate. This means, as a number of patents and trademarks filed are higher, that have higher marginal benefits. From this conclusion we can assume that marginal benefit of having broadband has a higher effect on high-income countries than in middle and low-income countries.

In brief, we can conclude that our estimation results provide powerful evidence that an increase in rate of broadband access promotes innovation. The effect is higher in high-income countries and smaller in low-income countries.

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